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PHYTOCHEMICAL PROFILE OF VARIOUS EXTRACTS OF *INDIGOFERA ASPALATHOIDES*

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ABSTRACT

Plants have played a major role in treatment of various diseases of animals and humans since time immemorial. More than 50% of all modern drugs are of natural origin and many of which have the ability to control and cure infections. A large number of active principles from traditional medicinal plants have been reported to have anti microbial properties. Most of the studies are based on individual chemicals with well defined mechanisms. India is endowed with a rich wealth of medicinal plants and it is one of the 12 mega bio-diversity centres having 45,000 plant species. In India around 20,000 medicinal plants have been recorded recently, but more than 500 traditional communities use 800 plant species for curing different diseases. Currently 80% of world population depends on plant derived medicines for human alleviation because of its slight side effects, easy availability and cost effectiveness. This plant is found abundantly in india. Phytochemical analysis was performed on extracts of Aqueous and ethanol [1:1] ethyl acetate, acetone, chloroform and propane, therefore it is of interest to investigate the phytochemical analysis of *Indigofera aspalathoides*.

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INTRODUCTION

Antibiotics have saved the lives of millions of people and have contributed to the major gains in life expectancy over the last century. However, the clinical efficacy of many existing antibiotics is being threatened by the emergence of multi-drug resistant pathogens [1]. The recent appearance of strains with reduced susceptibility as well as, undesirable side effects of certain antibiotics [2]. Infectious diseases caused by resistant microorganisms are associated with prolonged hospitalizations, increased cost, and greater risk for morbidity and mortality. Resistance is an especially vexing problem for people with impaired immune systems, such as AIDS, cancer patients and recipients of organ transplant. The promiscuous use of antibiotics accounts for a major part of the community burden of antibiotic use and contributes dramatically to the rising prevalence of resistance among major human pathogens. The effect is pronounced in third world as the costly replacement drugs for treating the highly resistant infectious diseases are unaffordable [3]. The resistance problem demands that a renewed effort be made to screen various medicinal plants for their potential antimicrobial traits, which are due to compounds synthesized in the secondary metabolism of the plant. The most important of these bioactive compounds of plants are alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds, steroids, resins, fatty acids and gums which are capable of producing definite physiological action on body. Another driving factor that encouraged scientists to search for new antimicrobial substances from various sources including medicinal plants has been the rapid rate of plant species extinction. Medicinal plants are relied upon by 80% of the world's population and in India there is a rich tradition of using herbal medicine for the treatment of various infectious diseases, inflammations, injuries and other diseases. Many of the plant materials used in traditional medicine are generally proved more effective and relatively cheaper than modern medicine [4]. against certain ailments while simultaneously mitigating many of the side effects that are often associated with synthetic antimicrobials [5]. The plant *Indigofera aspalathoides* is used as a potent drug for many diseases in the traditional Indian system. This plant belongs to the family Papilionaceae and it is commonly known as Sivanar Vembu or Iraivanar Vembuin Tamil language of India. The leaves, flowers, and tender shoots are said to be cooling and demulcent [6]. This plants used for the treatment of leprosy, syphilis, and various skin diseases [7]. The plant mainly contains saponins, tannins, steroids, alkaloids, flavonoids, and reducing sugars. The plant *Indigofera aspalathoides* is used for the treatment of chemically induced fibro sarcoma [8-15].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of samples

The medicinal plants used for the experiment were whole plant of *Indigofera aspalathoides* which were collected from the local medicinal farms.

Preparation of extracts

500 grams of dried leaf powder of *Indigofera aspalathoides* was packed in separate round bottom flask for sample extraction using different solvents namely ethanol, methanol, chloroform, ethyl acetate and water. The extraction was conducted with 750 ml of each solvent for a period of 24 hours. At the end of the extraction the respective solvents were concentrated under reduced pressure and the crude extracts were stored in refrigerator.

Phytochemical analysis

The extracts prepared were analyzed for the presence of alkaloids, saponin, tannins, steroids, flavonoids, anthraquinone, cardiac glycosides and reducing sugars based on the protocols available in the literature [16-20].

Test for alkaloids

The extract of the crude dry powder of each solvent was evaporated to dryness in boiling water bath. The residues were dissolved in 2 N Hydrochloric acid. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was divided into three equal portions. One portion was treated with a few drops of Mayer's reagent; one portion was treated with equal amount of Dragendorff's reagent and the third portion was treated with equal amount of Wagner's reagent respectively. The creamish precipitate, the orange precipitate and brown precipitate indicated the presence of respective alkaloids.

Test for saponins

About 0.5 g of the plant extract was shaken with water in a test tube and then heated to boil. Frothing was observed which was taken as a preliminary evidence for the presence of the saponin.

Test for tannins

About 0.5 g of extract was added was in 10 ml of water in a test tube and filtered. A few drops of 0.1% ferric chloride was added and observed for brownish green or blue-black coloration.

Test for steroids

2 ml of acetic anhydride was added to 0.5 g of methanol extract of each sample with 2 ml sulphuric acid. The colour changed from violet to blue or green in some samples indicating the presence of steroids.

Test for flavonoids

2 ml of extract solution was treated with 1.5 ml of 50% methanol solution. The solution was warmed and metal magnesium was added. To this solution few drops of conc. Hydrochloric acid was added and the red colour was observed for flavonoides and orange colour for flavonoids.

Test for anthraquinones

About 0.5 g of extract was taken in a dry test tube and 5 ml of chloroform was added and shaken for 5 min. The extract was filtered and the filtrate shaken with equal volume of 10% of ammonia solution. A pink violet or red colour in the ammonical layer indicates the presence of anthraquinones.

Test for cardiac glycosides

0.2 g of extract was dissolved in 1 ml of glacial acetic acid containing 1 drop of ferric chloride solution. This was then under layered with 1ml of concentrated sulphuric acid. A brown ring obtained at the interface indicated the presence of a deoxy sugar characteristic of cardiac glycosoids.

Test for Proteins

To 2ml of protein solution 1ml of 40% NaOH solution and 1 to 2 drops of 1% CuSO₄ solution was added. A violet color indicated the presence of peptide linkage of the molecule.

Test for Amino Acids

To 2ml of sample was added to 2ml of Ninhydrin reagent and kept in water bath for 20 minutes. Appearance of purple color indicated the presence of amino acids in the sample.

Test for Tri-Terpenoids

5ml of each extract was added to 2ml of chloroform and 3ml of con. H₂SO₄ to form a monolayer of reddish brown coloration of the interface was showed to form positive result for the terpenoids.

Test for Triple Sugar

To 2 ml of extract 2drops of Molisch's reagent was added and shaken well. 2ml of con. of con. H₂SO₄ was added on the sides of the test tube. A reddish violet ring appeared at the junction of two layers immediately indicated the presence of carbohydrates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sivanar vembu or Iraivan vembu in Tamil is botanically equated as *Indigofera aspalathoides* Vahl.ex.DC. belonging to the family Leguminosae. In Sanskrit it is Patakohomba or Sivanimba. Its leaves, flowers and tender shoots are cooling and demulcent, they are used in the form of decoction for leprosy and cancerous affections [21]. The leaves are also applied to abscesses. Roots are used as dentrifice, and also in mouth ulcers. The root is chewed in toothache and apathies. The whole plant is an ingredient of an oily preparation used for dandruff, syphilis and other skin affections. In Siddha system of medicine, the plant is prescribed for eczema, psoriasis, boils, burns, wounds, ulcers, and used also as an antidote to snake venom. Civanar vembu Tailam and Civanar vembuk kulit Tailam are two popular Siddha preparations used for various types of skin diseases including leprosy [22]. It is used along with camphor for different kinds of wounds. This plant is regarded as one used in Kayakalpa drugs and in the discovery of anticancer elixir. Water soluble fraction of alcoholic extract of dried tender shoots of *I. aspalathoides* showed significant anti inflammatory effect in experimental albino mice. As there is no record of phytochemical work of this highly potential traditional drug, present investigation is carried out and phyto chemical analysis of this plant is reported for the first time. Therefore, the present study was aimed to focus the various phytochemical constituents from various extracts of *Indigofera aspalathoides* have were investigated [23].

Table 1 Shows that the phyto chemical constituents of various extracts of *Indigofera aspalathoides*.

S:No	Phyto constituents	Aques extract	Ethyl Acetate Extract	Acetone extract	Chloroform extract	Propane extract
1	Flavanoids	+	+	+	+	+
2	Alkaloids	+	+	+	+	+
3	Tri Terpenoids	-	-	+	-	+
4	Saponins	+	+	+	-	-
5	Tannins	+	-	-	-	+
6	Triple Sugars	+	-	-	-	-
7	Amino acids	-	-	-	-	+
8	Anthroquinones	+	-	-	-	+
9	Steroids	+	+	+	+	+
10	Proteins	-	-	-	-	-
11	Cardiac glycosides	+	-	+	+	+
12	Polyphenols	+	+	-	-	+

“+” – Presence, “-” – Absence

The recent research showed that use of phytochemicals could slow down the onset and the progression of AD. Phytochemicals can be less toxic than new synthetic drugs. There are many questions concerning the mechanism of action, reproducibility, specific drug effects, and active ingredients of these herbal drugs. Among phytochemicals, those suitable to treat neurodegenerative diseases are compounds with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities. It was showed that regular intake of phytochemicals could improve health status through improving the antioxidant system, cognitive and physical performance, and increasing neuronal cell survival. Studies showed that polyphenols can play a key role in improvement of neurodegenerative disease. This seems to be elicited by oxidative stress and by interaction of neuroinflammatory mediators and plant based of natural antioxidants is considered as a primary preventive therapeutic measure as a protection against chronic neurological disorders [24]. Table 1 shows the phytochemical analysis of aqueous ethanol, ethyl acetate, acetone, chloroform and propane extracts of *I aspalathoides*. Phytochemical screening of the crude extracts revealed the presence steroids in all the extracts. Tri-terpenoids were present only in acetone and propane extracts and absent in rest of the extracts. Tanins are present in aqueous-ethanol and propane extract whereas tannins were absent other extracts. Proteins are absent in all the five extracts whereas the amino acids were present only in the propane extract. Triple sugar were present only in aqueous extract absent in all the five extracts. Anthraquinones were present in aqueous and ethanol and propane extract. Cardiac glycosides are present in ethyl acetate extract remaining were shown negative. Flavonoids and alkaloids were present in all the extracts. Saponins were present in chloroform and propane extracts remaining extracts shown negative result. The present study reveals that the presence of various phytochemical compounds in the traditional medicinal plant *Indigofera aspalathoides*.

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